

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years: 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals. 7%: 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage: Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing rice variety for irrigated lands

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Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing, dwarf (93 cm) rice variety was released recently in UP for cultivation in irrigated fields. It was developed in Sri Lanka from the cross IR262/Remadja

and tested in the International Rice Observational Nursery as BG90-2 in 1974. The plants have good tillering capacity, mature in 126-132 d, and have high yield potential. Grains are long, slender, and translucent, with good cooking quality. It is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya, which has become susceptible.

Pant Dhan 4 was tested in station trials from 1976 to 1980 and in state variety trials from 1979 to 1982 (see table). □

Performance of Pant Dhan 4 in state variety trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial center	Grain yield (t/ha)				Days to maturity	
	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya	CD at 5%	CV in %	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya
<i>1981 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	4.6	4.6	0.1	1.8	134	131
Bareilly	7.0	6.7	0.2	2.1	133	141
Haldwani	7.2	5.4	1.2	12.4	139	143
Hardoi	4.1	4.3	0.2	4.3	124	135
Mathura	5.1	4.8	0.3	4.5	123	130
Meerut	2.0	1.7	0.3	12.6	140	141
Jhansi	2.1	2.5	0.6	16.1	123	127
Barabanki	3.2	3.6	0.4	7.9	122	129
Etawah	3.1	4.3	1.0	20.6	122	126
Varanasi	3.1	3.5	1.5	12.0	110	126
Average	4.2	4.2	–	–	126	133
<i>1982 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	3.8	4.5	0.09	1.73	131	133
Bareilly	5.9	5.6	0.07	0.75	132	139
Haldwani	5.8	5.5	0.9	9.8	152	154
Hardoi	4.8	4.7	0.3	5.3	130	138
Mathura	4.3	4.6	0.2	3.2	115	128
Meerut	6.3	4.5	1.0	10.8	139	139
Jhansi	5.6	4.1	n.s.	22.2	129	137
Barabanki	–	–	–	–	–	–
Etawah	–	–	–	–	–	–
Varanasi	–	–	–	–	–	–
Average	5.2	4.9	–	–	132	138

Performance of IR50 during sornavari (summer) season

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In Tamil Nadu, sornavari is from May to Sep. Short-duration (100-120 d) rice varieties are grown. TKM9 (TKM7/IR8)

Yield characteristics of short-duration varieties at Tirur, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
TKM9	111	450	5.6
IR50	113	415	5.1
ADT36	117	380	5.0
IET4786	118	380	4.6
PY2	108	405	4.5